

SHERLOCK

Supporting the energy transition of the building stock

Multidisciplinary teaching and training methods based on micro-credentials

Guidelines for educators

Michal Krajčík
Anna Predajnianska
Dušan Petráš

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Contributor(s)	Michal Krajčík Anna Predajnianska Dušan Petráš
Reviewers	Pablo Baigorria Kobylinski (CREARA) Vincenzo Bianco (UNIPARTHENOPE) Mattia De Rosa (UNIGE) Carmelina Cosmi (CNR)
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UNICAMPANIA	Università Degli Studi Della Campania Luigi Vanvitelli
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List of acronyms

Acronym	Meaning
ACE	Approved Consultant / Educator
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ECTS	European Credit Transfer and Accumulation system
EEFIG	European Energy Efficiency Financing Coalition
EQF	European Qualification Framework
EU	European Union
HEI	Higher Education Institutions
IoT	Internet of Things
LCA	Life Cycle Analysis
MOOC	Massive Open Online Courses
NZEB	Nearly Zero Energy Building
RES4CITY	Renewable Energies Systems for Cities - project
VET	Vocational Education and Training

Executive summary

Deliverable D6.2, “*Multidisciplinary Teaching and Training Methods Based on Microcredentials – Guidelines for Educators*”, provides practical guidance for educators, higher education institutions, VET providers, trainers, and other organisations interested in designing learning programmes based on microcredentials. The deliverable uses the SHERLOCK project as an example of how such an approach can be applied in the field of building renovation.

The document presents the main components of microcredential-based education programmes. It explains how microcredentials, micromaster structures, MOOC-based learning, digital certificates, case-study-based teaching, stakeholder co-design, monitoring, and assessment can be combined into a coherent learning pathway. A central part of the deliverable is the methodology for designing such microcredential-based programmes. The deliverable also explains how individual courses can be structured in practice through video lectures, reading materials, reinforcement questions, exercises, case studies, digital tools, and assessments.

Monitoring and assessment are presented as essential elements of microcredential-based learning. Assessment should verify whether learners have achieved the expected competences, while monitoring should help educators improve the course based on learner progress, completion data, feedback, and stakeholder validation. Digital certificates or credential records should be linked to learning outcomes and acquired competences.

The final part of the deliverable provides concrete recommendations for educators. These cover educational needs identification and assessment, stakeholder co-design, learning outcome definition and microcredential identification, micromaster structure, teaching material preparation, monitoring and assessment strategies, and integration of innovative teaching tools. Practical examples are used to illustrate how these recommendations can be applied in practice.

The main takeaway of the deliverable is that microcredentials should be more than short online courses. They should be structured and practice-oriented learning units. Each microcredential should have a clear target group, defined skills need, measurable learning outcomes, suitable teaching materials, and transparent assessment. Where relevant, microcredentials should be designed so that they can be combined into broader learning pathways, such as micromaster programmes or professional training courses.

1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose and scope of the deliverable

Deliverable D6.2, “*Multidisciplinary teaching and training methods based on microcredentials – Guidelines for educators*”, has been developed within Work Package 6 of the SHERLOCK project. It focuses on the methodological aspects required to design and deliver microcredential-based programmes. The deliverable provides practical guidance for educators, higher education institutions (HEI), vocational education and training (VET) providers, trainers, and other organisations interested in designing and implementing multidisciplinary learning programmes based on microcredentials.

The scope of the deliverable is twofold. First, it presents the main components of a microcredential-based educational framework, including the role of microcredentials, micromaster structures, MOOC-based learning, digital certificates, and case-study-based teaching. Second, it uses the experience gained within the SHERLOCK project as an example and translates it into practical recommendations that can be used to develop similar programmes in other contexts. The final section provides concrete recommendations on:

- (i) educational needs identification and assessment;
- (ii) stakeholder co-design framework set-up;
- (iii) learning objective definition and microcredential identification;
- (iv) micromaster structure definition;
- (v) monitoring and assessment strategies;
- (vi) integration and utilization of the proposed innovative teaching tools.

The document is intended as an open guideline resource. It does not prescribe a single rigid model but proposes a flexible methodology that can be adapted to different educational levels, professional profiles, institutional settings, and thematic areas. Although the SHERLOCK project focuses on the energy renovation of buildings, the proposed approach may also be transferred to other sectors where multidisciplinary green and digital skills are required, such as renewable energy, sustainable transport, circular economy, smart cities, and climate-neutral urban development.

1.2 Context of the energy transition of the building stock

Buildings represent the largest end-user sector in terms of energy consumption at the EU level. They account for approximately 40% of the EU’s total energy consumption and around 35% of energy-related greenhouse gas emissions. As a result, improving the energy performance of buildings is a key priority for achieving the European Union’s climate and energy objectives. In line with EU’s

long-term climate targets, the building sector must be progressively decarbonized by 2050 [1, 2]. This transition requires the large-scale implementation of energy efficiency measures and the adoption of sustainable renovation practices across the building stock.

Developing effective retrofitting strategies is therefore essential, as a significant proportion of existing buildings were constructed before modern energy performance standards were introduced. Approximately 35% of the EU building stock is more than 50 years old, while nearly 75% of buildings are considered energy inefficient. Despite the urgent need for improvements, the current rate of renovation remains relatively low, with only about 1% of buildings undergoing renovation each year [3].

Public buildings are expected to lead by example. Under the revised Energy Efficiency Directive, EU countries must renovate 3% of the total useful floor area of public buildings each year, with the obligation extended beyond central government buildings to public buildings at local, regional and national level where the relevant floor-area threshold is met [4]. The energy performance of buildings across Europe is also monitored by the EU Building Stock Observatory (BSO) web tool, which, in addition to providing data on the EU's building stock, supports the monitoring of current EU energy policies and measures, thereby contributing to the decision-making process [5]

1.3 Target audience of the guidelines

The present guidelines are intended for organisations and professionals involved in the design, delivery, assessment, and recognition of educational and training programmes based on microcredentials [6]. In particular, the document addresses educators and institutions that aim to develop flexible, multidisciplinary learning pathways supporting lifelong learning, upskilling, and reskilling in the field of building energy renovation and related sectors.

The primary target audience includes HEI, in particular academic staff, course coordinators, programme designers, and e-learning teams involved in the development of microcredential-based courses and study programmes. For these actors, the guidelines provide recommendations on how to define learning objectives, structure modular learning units, integrate case studies and align assessment methods with learning outcomes.

A second key target group is represented by vocational education and training (VET) providers. VET organisations can use the guidelines to design shorter, practice-oriented training courses for professionals who need to update their skills in response to the changing requirements of the building renovation sector.

The document is also relevant for professional trainers, lifelong learning providers, and MOOC developers. These actors can use the described methodology to create accessible and flexible learning experiences for learners with different backgrounds and professional profiles.

In addition, the guidelines are addressed to industry, financial institutions, public authorities, professional associations, and other stakeholders involved in the co-design and validation of education and training programmes. Their contribution is essential to ensure that microcredentials respond to actual labour-market needs. These stakeholders may contribute by identifying skills gaps, validating learning outcomes, providing case studies, supporting dissemination, and facilitating the recognition of acquired competences.

Finally, the guidelines may be useful for project coordinators, policy actors, and organisations interested in replicating the present approach in other sectors or geographical contexts. Although the document is rooted in the specific experience of SHERLOCK, its recommendations are transferable to other areas where multidisciplinary green and digital skills are needed.

1.4 Relevance of the SHERLOCK educational approach

These guidelines support educators in designing multidisciplinary teaching and training methods based on microcredentials. The experience gained within the SHERLOCK project is particularly relevant because it provides a practical example of implementing such methods across different institutions and European countries. SHERLOCK is therefore used in these guidelines to illustrate a microcredential-based learning framework in practice, particularly in the field of building energy renovation, where technical, financial, environmental, digital, and transversal competences need to be developed together (Table 1).

A key barrier in building renovation is that public funding alone is not sufficient to achieve the European Union's 2050 climate neutrality targets, and private investment is essential. However, financial institutions often lack the technical expertise needed to evaluate energy renovation projects, while technical professionals and project developers often lack the financial and business knowledge needed to communicate effectively with investors. This creates a skills mismatch that limits cooperation between technical and financial actors.

To address this challenge, SHERLOCK promotes a multidisciplinary educational framework based on microcredentials, case-study learning, stakeholder co-design, and MOOC-based delivery. The project aims to support technical professionals in acquiring business and financial competences while simultaneously helping financial and business professionals understand the technical principles of energy efficiency, building renovation, and sustainability assessment.

The SHERLOCK educational approach focuses on developing both green and digital skills. Green skills include the evaluation of energy, environmental, and economic benefits of energy efficiency measures, as well as the assessment of non-energy benefits such as improved sustainability and reduced urban environmental impact. Digital skills are linked to the use of assessment tools, data analysis, uncertainty evaluation, and digital solutions supporting energy renovation and building performance optimisation.

To address these needs, SHERLOCK develops a flexible educational framework consisting of MOOC-based micromaster programmes, short training courses, microcredentials, and practical case studies. The framework is co-designed with higher education institutions, VET providers, companies, financial institutions, and other stakeholders through the SHERLOCK Knowledge Centres. In SHERLOCK, Knowledge Centres are stakeholder cooperation hubs established to connect education providers with actors from the building renovation and financial sectors. Their role is to support dialogue between these groups, identify skills gaps, validate learning outcomes, and review the relevance of training content. This collaboration ensures that the educational content reflects real labour-market needs.

Table 1. Relationship of the guidelines with SHERLOCK objectives

SHERLOCK element	Relationship with the guidelines (D6.2)
Project objectives	D6.2 supports the development and transfer of green and digital skills for building energy renovation.
Knowledge Centres	D6.2 draws on the stakeholder co-design approach promoted through the Knowledge Centres.
Micromaster programme	D6.2 provides guidance on how to structure multidisciplinary micromaster programmes based on stackable microcredentials.
Short training course	D6.2 supports the design of flexible and practice-oriented training for professionals and VET learners.
Case studies	D6.2 explains how real-life case studies can be integrated into teaching and learning activities.
Teaching materials	D6.2 provides recommendations for preparing online learning materials, video lectures, exercises, readings, and assessment tools.
Piloting and feedback	D6.2 incorporates monitoring and assessment principles to support continuous improvement of microcredential-based programmes.
Exploitation and sustainability	D6.2 contributes to the replicability and transferability of the SHERLOCK educational model.

2. Concept and methodology for microcredential-based learning

This chapter presents the general concept and methodology behind multidisciplinary microcredential-based learning. It explains why microcredentials are useful for addressing complex skills gaps and how they are designed through needs analysis, stakeholder engagement, learning-outcome definition, course development, monitoring and improvement.

2.1. Rationale for multidisciplinary microcredential-based education

Multidisciplinary microcredential-based education is particularly relevant in sectors where professional challenges cannot be solved from a single disciplinary perspective. Areas such as building energy renovation, renewable energy, sustainable transport, circular economy and smart cities require the combination of technical, financial, environmental, digital, regulatory and communication competences. Traditional education and training pathways often address these competences separately, which may limit cooperation between professionals from different sectors.

Microcredentials provide a flexible way to address this challenge. They allow educators to organise learning into short, focused and assessable units that can respond to specific skills gaps, support lifelong learning, and enable professionals to update their competences without enrolling in a full degree programme. When combined into a coherent pathway, microcredentials can support both targeted upskilling and broader multidisciplinary learning.

The SHERLOCK project is used in these guidelines as an example of how this approach can be applied in the field of building energy renovation. In this sector, cooperation between technical and financial actors is essential, but often difficult. Financial institutions may lack the technical expertise needed to evaluate energy renovation projects, while technical professionals may lack the financial and business knowledge needed to communicate effectively with investors. A microcredential-based framework can help address this skills mismatch by creating learning pathways that build complementary competences and a shared professional language.

2.2. Framework for designing microcredential-based programmes

A microcredential-based educational framework should be developed through a structured methodology that links educational needs, stakeholder input, learning objectives, course design, piloting, monitoring and continuous improvement. Such a methodology helps ensure that the learning offer is not only academically coherent, but also relevant for learners and professional practice.

A general methodology for designing microcredential-based programmes may include the following phases:

- (i) **Analysis of educational and labour-market needs.** This includes identification of learners, skills gaps and professional challenges.
- (ii) **Stakeholder engagement and education co-design.** Stakeholders involve education providers, industry, employers, public authorities, professional organisations and learners.
- (iii) **Definition of learning outcomes and microcredential topics.** Translate identified needs into competences and learning units.
- (iv) **Development of teaching materials and learning tools.** Include videos, readings, exercises, case studies, digital tools.
- (v) **Piloting and delivery.** Use online or blended platforms to test the learning pathway with the target audience.
- (vi) **Monitoring, assessment and revision.** Use learner performance, feedback and stakeholder validation to improve the course.
- (vii) **Dissemination and transferability.** Ensure that the methodology and learning resources can be reused or adapted in other contexts.

In SHERLOCK, this general methodology is applied to the development of a multidisciplinary educational framework for building energy renovation. The project uses stakeholder co-design, Knowledge Centres, MOOC-based delivery, microcredentials, micromaster pathways and case-study learning to support the acquisition of green, digital, technical, financial and transversal competences. Fig. 1 illustrates the SHERLOCK methodological framework as a practical example of the broader design logic.

Figure 1 – SHERLOCK's methodological framework

3. Educational tools and implementation approaches

This chapter presents the main educational framework and tools used to design and deliver microcredential-based learning. It focuses on online learning platforms, micromaster structures, microcredential course design, teaching materials, microcredential baskets, and case-study-based learning.

3.1. Open innovation, sustainability and transferability

Microcredential-based education benefits from open innovation because it often extends beyond a single institution, discipline, or sector. In microcredential-based education, open innovation means that courses are not designed only by one institution or teacher. Instead, educators work with companies, public authorities, professional organisations, learners, and other stakeholders to identify skills needs and develop learning content that is relevant for practice.

A well-designed educational framework should remain useful beyond the initial course delivery and should be adaptable to other learner groups and thematic areas. This requires clear learning outcomes, modular course structures, accessible digital materials, transparent assessment methods, and documentation that allows to replicate or adapt the approach.

In the SHERLOCK project, these principles are applied through a multidisciplinary educational framework focused on the energy renovation of buildings. The main elements of this framework include:

- **microcredentials**, which organise learning into short and focused units addressing specific skills needs;
- **MOOC delivery**, which enables flexible access to the courses through the BoostMySkills platform;
- **case-study learning**, which uses real examples to help learners analyse technical solutions, financial feasibility, environmental impacts, and stakeholder roles in practical contexts;
- **stakeholder co-design**, which involves various stakeholders in identifying skills needs and validating educational content;
- **micromaster structure**, which combines individual microcredentials into broader learning pathways for different target groups;
- **digital recognition**, which supports the certification and communication of acquired competences;
- **transferability**, since the modular structure allows the approach to be adapted to other sectors.

3.2. MOOC courses and online learning platforms

MOOC courses, from the English term **Massive Open Online Courses**, are online courses that make learning content accessible to a large number of participants without significant entry barriers (Fig. 2). In microcredential-based education, MOOCs are particularly useful because they support flexible access to learning materials, self-paced study, and participation by learners from different geographical, educational, and professional backgrounds.

Figure 2 – Illustration picture of Massive Open Online Courses

MOOC platforms support the transparency and recognition of learning outcomes. They allow educators to structure content into sections, subsections, and learning units, monitor learner progress, collect feedback, and issue digital certificates after completion. This makes them suitable also for assessment, quality assurance, and competence recognition. However, educators should also consider common limitations, such as lower completion rates, the need for learner self-discipline, limited direct interaction with instructors, and the importance of clear course guidance and support.

Among the most well-known providers of MOOC courses are Coursera, edX, Udacity, FutureLearn, EduOpen or BoostMySkills which is used by SHERLOCK. These platforms cooperate with universities, research institutions, and industry experts, offering courses in various areas.

3.2.1. Example from SHERLOCK: BoostMySkills platform

The SHERLOCK courses are available at the online MOOC platform BoostMySkills. The platform focuses on helping users identify skill gaps, access relevant training programmes, and strengthen both technical and transversal skills required in a rapidly changing labour market.

A key feature of BoostMySkills is its learner-centred approach. Users can typically access personalised learning pathways, online courses, microlearning modules, and competency-based training resources tailored to their professional goals. These may include areas such as digital skills, sustainability, management, communication, and entrepreneurship.

The platform is particularly relevant in the context of upskilling and reskilling. As labour market demands evolve due to digitalisation, automation, and the green transition, platforms such as BoostMySkills help individuals remain competitive by continuously updating their knowledge and capabilities. For employers, it can also serve as a tool for workforce development.

Another important aspect of BoostMySkills is the integration of credential systems, which may include certificates, badges, or microcredentials that validate completed learning achievements. These recognitions can be digitally shared to increase the visibility of acquired competencies.

3.3. Micromaster definition and structure

Micromaster programmes are structured learning pathways composed of several smaller learning units, such as microcredentials. They are designed to provide learners with competences in a specific thematic area. Learners may follow the full pathway or complete selected microcredentials according to their professional needs.

In lifelong learning, micromasters can support upskilling and reskilling by combining short, focused courses into a broader educational programme. This is particularly useful for professionals who need to update their knowledge while continuing their work. It also allows educators to organise complex topics into manageable learning units with clearly defined learning outcomes, workload, teaching materials and assessment methods.

A micromaster structure is especially useful when different learner groups need complementary competences. For example, one pathway may provide technical learners with financial competences, while another pathway may provide financial learners with technical and environmental knowledge. This makes the

micromaster format suitable for sectors where cooperation across disciplines is necessary.

3.3.1. Educational objectives of the micromasters

The educational objectives describe the overall competences that learners are expected to acquire by completing the full pathway. A well-designed micromaster should have a clear target audience, a well-defined competence and a transparent structure. The learning pathway should explain who the programme is for, which skills gaps it addresses and how the individual microcredentials contribute to the educational objective.

In micromaster programmes, participants can study at their own pace while continuing their professional careers. Successful completion may provide academic credit or accelerated admission into selected full study programmes at participating universities. This creates a bridge between short-form online learning and formal higher education. The programmes can be particularly valuable for individuals planning to reskill or upskill.

3.3.2. Example from SHERLOCK: micromaster curricula

The SHERLOCK micromaster programme is divided into two curricula tailored to the needs of two different target audiences.

Curriculum 1 – technical professionals: this curriculum aims to equip technical professionals, such as engineers, architects and building managers, with relevant skills and competences in business and management. The main topics include contractual business models, green financing and energy governance. These are complemented by transversal skills such as decision-making tools, communication strategies and public relations.

Curriculum 2 – financial/business professionals: this curriculum aims to equip financial and business professionals, such as credit institutions, investors and portfolio managers, with relevant skills and competences in the energy sector. The main topics include building energy consumption, energy auditing, energy efficiency strategies, renewable energies, circular economy and energy renovation strategies. These are complemented by transversal skills that support cooperation and communication with technical actors.

This structure illustrates how a micromaster can be used to address a multidisciplinary skills gap. Each curriculum responds to the needs of a specific learner group. The overall programme supports the development of a common understanding between technical and financial actors.

3.4. Microcredential course structure and learning materials

This section explains how a microcredential can be structured as a coherent online learning experience. It focuses on the organisation of course content, design of learning units, preparation of learning materials and creation of a microcredential basket.

3.4.1. Structure of microcredentials in online learning platforms

In online learning platforms, microcredentials are usually structured as flexible courses that learners can follow according to their own pace and availability. To support clear progression, course content is commonly divided into sections, subsections, and learning units. This structure helps educators organise the content into manageable parts.

A learning unit typically focuses on one specific topic or concept. It may include a short video lecture, reading materials, reinforcement questions, practical examples, or other supporting resources. Several units can be grouped into a subsection, while several subsections can form a larger course section. This allows dividing complex multidisciplinary topics into smaller learning steps.

In SHERLOCK, the microcredentials are organised on the BoostMySkills platform as flexible online courses, usually lasting between 4 and 8 weeks. Each course is structured into sections, and each section is composed of smaller learning units that represent the basic building blocks of the course. A unit typically consists of a video lecture, reinforcement questions, and reading materials. The platform also allows units to be grouped into subsections, which may combine different types of learning resources and activities.

Figure 3 – Example of MOOC structure for microcredential

In the SHERLOCK example, the main elements of a subsection include:

- a series of multimedia videos, usually lasting 4 to 10 minutes, explaining the basic concepts;
- reading materials that provide additional perspectives, examples, case studies, or exercises;
- exercises or test-type reinforcement questions that help students consolidate their learning.

3.4.2. Microcredential learning unit and section design

Once the general course structure is defined, educators should decide how the content will be distributed across sections and learning units. The main objective is to create a learning sequence that is manageable, coherent, and aligned with the expected learning outcomes.

In SHERLOCK, one section corresponds approximately to one week of study, representing several hours of learner workload per week (Fig. 4). This enables learners organise their study time and supports gradual progression through the course.

Figure 4 – Example of SHERLOCK microcredential structure

Each learning unit focuses on a single concept or skill. This makes the content easier to understand and allows learners to return to specific topics when needed. Videos should therefore be concise and supported by materials such as presentations, PDF readings, examples, or exercises.

Reinforcement exercises are included to help learners check their understanding during the course. In SHERLOCK, these exercises usually take the form of multiple-choice questions. They are used for self-assessment and knowledge consolidation, not as part of the final grade.

At the end of each microcredential, learners complete a final assessment composed of several questions or tasks. This assessment verifies whether the learner has acquired the expected knowledge and competences linked to the microcredential.

3.4.3. Teaching materials preparation

Online learning usually requires a combination of multiple teaching materials such as video lectures, reading materials, presentations, exercises, case studies, software tools, calculation sheets, and final assessment materials. Each video, reading, exercise or case study should support a specific competence or learning outcome.

In SHERLOCK, each microcredential is provided with relevant teaching material. It was recommended that approximately five hours of video lectures per ECTS should be prepared. Consequently, each 3 ECTS microcredential includes approximately 15 hours of video lectures, together with the necessary teaching aids, such as notes, software, calculation sheets, exercises, and other supporting resources.

All SHERLOCK materials are developed in English to reach the widest possible audience during the pilot phase. Furthermore, all videos are subtitled to maximise accessibility and support learners from different countries. The learning process is also supported by case studies, as discussed in Section 3.5.

3.4.4. Methodology for creating a microcredential basket

A microcredential basket is a coherent set of microcredentials designed to address a broader educational or professional objective. Instead of developing individual microcredentials as isolated courses, educators should define how they complement each other, which target groups they serve, and how they can be combined into a wider learning pathway.

The creation of a microcredential basket can be summarised into 7 steps (see also Table 2):

- (i) **Identify the target learner groups.** Define who the microcredentials are intended for, what their educational or professional background is, and what type of upskilling or reskilling they need.
- (ii) **Find skills gaps and educational needs.** Identify which competences are missing or insufficiently developed in the target group. This analysis may be based on stakeholder consultation, labour-market needs, existing training gaps, policy priorities.
- (iii) **Translate needs into learning outcomes.** Define what learners should know, understand, or be able to do after completing the microcredential. Learning outcomes should be specific, measurable, and suitable for assessment
- (iv) **Group learning outcomes into microcredential topics.** Each microcredential should focus on a clearly defined competence area

and have standalone value. Individual microcredentials should complement each other and contribute to the objective of the basket.

- (v) **Organise the basket into a learning pathway.** Decide which microcredentials are common for all learners, which are specific to particular target groups, and how they can be combined into a micromaster or professional training programme.
- (vi) **Validate the proposed basket with stakeholders.** Involve education providers, VET organisations, companies, financial institutions, public authorities, professional organisations, and learners to verify whether the proposed topics and learning outcomes are relevant for practice.
- (vii) **Connect the basket with teaching, assessment, and recognition.** Each microcredential has appropriate learning materials, assessment activities aligned with the learning outcomes, and clear information for certification or digital badges.

In the SHERLOCK project, this process is demonstrated through the development of a microcredential basket for building energy renovation. The process started from the identification of two main learner groups: technical professionals who need stronger financial and business competences, and financial/business professionals who need a better understanding of energy efficiency and technical project assessment.

The identified skills gaps included green skills, digital skills, technical competences, financial and business competences, and transversal skills such as communication, decision-making, and stakeholder cooperation. These needs were translated into learning objectives and grouped into microcredentials. The process was supported by the Knowledge Centres, which involve HEI, VET providers, companies, financial institutions, public authorities, and other relevant stakeholders. This helped ensure that the microcredential basket reflected real professional needs of technical and financial actors.

Table 2. Steps in the development of a microcredential basket

Step	Main question	Output
1. Target group definition	Who are the learners?	Learner profiles
2. Skills-gap analysis	What competences are missing?	Priority educational needs
3. Learning outcomes	What should learners be able to do?	Measurable learning outcomes
4. Topic grouping	Which outcomes belong together?	Individual microcredential topics
5. Pathway design	How do microcredentials connect?	Micromaster pathway
6. Stakeholder validation	Is the basket relevant for practice?	Validated microcredential basket
7. Teaching and assessment	How is learning delivered and assessed?	Materials, assessment methods, badge information

3.4.5. Example from SHERLOCK: overview of microcredentials

The SHERLOCK micromaster includes a set of microcredentials covering technical, financial, environmental, digital and transversal topics. The microcredentials are designed to support the acquisition of multidisciplinary competences required for the energy transition of the building stock (Table 3).

Table 3. List of microcredentials released in the SHERLOCK project

No.	Name on the microcredential	Partner
MC01	Basic of energy efficiency	UNICAMP
MC02	Decision making towards sustainable buildings	LEI
MC03	Environmental social governance finance	EPTA
MC04	Advertising and public relations in the energy sector	VMU
MC05	Systemic design for energy retrofiting	3OC
MC06	Energy auditing of buildings	STUBA
MC07	Incorporation of natural materials in energy renovation of buildings	TUC
MC08	Life cycle analysis in construction	LNGE
MC09	Circular economy in built environment	CECOLAB
MC10	Energy consumption in buildings	UNIGE
MC11	Green infrastructure finance	NUIM
MC12	Communication strategies with financial institutions	EPTA
MC13	Business model for energy efficiency in buildings	CREARA
MC14	Energy performance contracting	STUBA
MC15	Probabilistic approach for energy efficiency evaluation	UNIPARTH

The Micromasters programmes are available on the BoostMySkills platform, where course participants can view the course content and learning objectives. An example of a SHERLOCK microcredential on the BoostMySkills platform is shown in Fig.5. A short description of the microcredentials is provided in Table 4.

Table 4. Short description of microcredentials released in the SHERLOCK project

MC01 Basic of energy efficiency	The microcredential highlights the importance of energy efficiency in reducing energy costs, protecting the environment, and promoting sustainability while addressing global energy challenges and climate change. Participants gain knowledge of energy-saving practices and their economic and environmental benefits, enabling them to contribute to a more sustainable future.
MC02 Decision making towards sustainable buildings	This microcredential provides learners with knowledge about sustainable building renovation, decision-making processes, and their impact on energy efficiency and city sustainability. Participants gain an understanding of renovation approaches across Europe and learn how citizen involvement and decision-making influence sustainability at building, neighbourhood, and city levels.

<p>MC03 Environmental social governance finance</p>	<p>This microcredential introduces ESG finance, explaining how financial institutions support sustainable investments and the challenges of avoiding greenwashing. Participants gain knowledge of integrating ESG factors into financial decision-making and develop a better understanding of sustainable finance practices and their role in investment activities.</p>
<p>MC04 Advertising and public relations in the energy sector</p>	<p>This microcredential provides learners with knowledge and skills in advertising and public relations to support sustainable practices and communication in the energy sector. Participants learn to develop, implement, and evaluate communication strategies while understanding key factors and trends influencing advertising, public relations, and crisis communication.</p>
<p>MC05 Systemic design for energy retrofitting</p>	<p>This microcredential introduces systemic design approaches for sustainable energy retrofitting, covering systems thinking, stakeholder engagement, data-informed decision-making, and strategic planning. Participants gain skills in developing business models, scaling retrofitting solutions, and applying innovative strategies to support sustainable energy transitions.</p>
<p>MC06 Energy auditing of buildings</p>	<p>This microcredential explains the role of energy audits in identifying cost-effective energy-saving measures and improving building sustainability and energy performance. Participants learn the differences between energy auditing and certification, the audit process, and when energy audits are required.</p>
<p>MC07 Incorporation of natural materials in energy renovation of buildings</p>	<p>This microcredential introduces sustainable natural materials for energy-efficient building renovation, focusing on their technical, economic, and environmental aspects. Participants gain knowledge of innovative materials, certification standards, and strategies for integrating natural solutions into sustainable renovation projects.</p>
<p>MC08 Life cycle analysis in construction</p>	<p>This microcredential provides a non-technical introduction to energy efficiency, highlighting its importance in reducing costs, supporting sustainability, and improving environmental responsibility. Participants gain practical knowledge of energy-saving practices and their economic and environmental benefits, enabling them to contribute to a more sustainable future.</p>
<p>MC09 Circular economy in built environment</p>	<p>This microcredential introduces Circular Economy principles and sustainable solutions for the built environment, focusing on resource efficiency, energy performance, and decarbonization strategies. Participants gain practical skills in circularity methods, environmental impact assessment, and applying sustainable approaches to support a more resilient future.</p>
<p>MC10 Energy consumption in buildings</p>	<p>This microcredential introduces building energy consumption concepts, assessment methods, and strategies to improve energy performance and reduce carbon emissions. Participants gain knowledge of energy efficiency measures, renewable energy integration, and technologies to reduce heating and cooling demands at building and district levels.</p>
<p>MC11 Green infrastructure finance</p>	<p>This microcredential explores the financial and economic aspects of sustainable infrastructure, focusing on green investments, sustainable finance instruments, and financing strategies for low-carbon development. Participants gain knowledge of risk assessment, regulatory frameworks, and impact evaluation to support planning and investment in sustainable infrastructure projects.</p>

MC12 Communication strategies with financial institutions	This microcredential equips entrepreneurs and business professionals with knowledge and skills to secure financing for green business transformation projects. Participants learn how to prepare financing applications, understand financial evaluation criteria, and apply negotiation strategies to successfully obtain green financing.
MC13 Business model for energy efficiency in buildings	This microcredential explores financial strategies and innovative business models that support energy efficiency projects in buildings and help unlock private investment. Participants gain knowledge of financial instruments and funding mechanisms to improve the viability and implementation of sustainable energy solutions.
MC14 Energy performance contracting	This microcredential introduces energy performance contracting (EPC) as a method for improving building energy efficiency through agreements with guaranteed energy savings. Participants gain knowledge of EPC structures, implementation processes, financial aspects, and key elements required for successful energy efficiency projects.
MC15 Probabilistic approach for energy efficiency evaluation	This microcredential provides learners with knowledge and skills to evaluate energy efficiency measures in buildings using probabilistic modelling, data analysis, and financial assessment methods. Participants learn to make informed, data-driven decisions by assessing energy-saving strategies while considering uncertainties in real-world conditions.

Probabilistic Approach for Energy Efficiency Evaluation

by Università degli Studi di Napoli Parthenope

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Context and Overview

The Probabilistic Approach for the Evaluation of Energy Efficiency Measures MC is designed to equip professionals with the skills and knowledge needed to address the critical challenges of energy efficiency and financial analysis within the context of building sustainability. In an age marked by environmental concerns and the need for cost-effective energy solutions, this MC offers a comprehensive understanding of how to evaluate and implement energy-saving measures in buildings. Learners will delve into the core principles of probabilistic modelling, data analysis, and financial evaluation, gaining practical insights into assessing the impact of energy efficiency measures while accounting for uncertainties in real-world scenarios. This MC empowers individuals to make informed, data-driven decisions regarding the implementation of energy-saving strategies in buildings.

Learning Objectives

On the completion of the micro-credential, participants will be able to:

- Recall key concepts and principles related to energy efficiency measures in buildings.
- Explain the probabilistic approach for evaluating energy efficiency measures.
- Describe the relationship between energy conservation and financial sustainability.
- Apply probabilistic modelling techniques to analyse energy efficiency measures.
- Evaluate the potential impact and risks associated with energy efficiency strategies within a probabilistic framework.

Course Number: MC15 | SHERLOCK

Up to 15hrs per week for 5 weeks

Sections

- Introduction to the Evaluation of Energy Efficiency Measures
- The Energy Renovation Tool - A practical approach for Deterministic and Probabilistic evaluations
- Using the ERV-Tool
- Final Exam

Created and delivered by:

Professor Vincenzo Bianco
UNIPARTHENOPE

Figure 5 – Microcredential example on BoostMySkills platform

3.5. Case-study-based learning

Case-study-based learning is a teaching methodology based on the use of realistic situations to illustrate the application of concepts and methods. It is commonly used in management and business education, but it can also be highly effective in technical, financial, environmental, and digital education.

In microcredential-based learning, case studies are particularly useful because they help learners move from theoretical knowledge to practical application. They may be used to introduce a practical problem, demonstrate the use of a digital tool, support a calculation exercise, stimulate discussion, or form part of the final assessment.

Case studies are especially valuable in multidisciplinary education because they allow learners to examine one problem from different perspectives, such as technical feasibility, financial viability, environmental impact, implementation barriers, social relevance. This is important in sectors such as building energy renovation, where solutions cannot be evaluated only from one viewpoint.

3.5.1. Selection and thematic coverage of SHERLOCK case studies

SHERLOCK uses the “case studies education” in its courses. The project developed 10 case studies focusing on a multidisciplinary approach. The selected topics reflect the main areas addressed by the SHERLOCK educational framework. The case studies cover both **green skills** and **digital skills**, as shown in Table 5.

Table 5. List of SHERLOCK case studies

Case Study Title	Skill Domain	Author
Evaluating Building Energy Retrofitting Strategies Under Uncertainty	Digital Skills	UNIGE
Technical Perspective of the Integration of Energy Retrofit and Renewable Energy Sources in Buildings with Solar Chimney	Green Skills	UNICAMPANIA
Unveiling the Nexus: Exploring the Relationship Between Building Energy Retrofit, Non-Energy Benefits, and Energy Poverty	Green Skills	UNIPARTH
Technical And Financial Analysis of Energy Retrofit for a Residential Building	Green Skills	STUBA
The Role of Machine Learning in Retrofitting Buildings to Support the Development of Smart Cities: Case Study in Mullingar Town, Ireland	Digital Skills	NUIM
Development of a Simple Digital Tool for Buildings Energy Efficiency Estimations	Digital Skills	VMU
Impact of Digitalisation on Energy Consumption in Buildings	Digital Skills	LEI

Innovative Business Models for Supporting Deep Energy Renovation of Households	Green Skills	CREARA
Promoting Circularity in Building Energy Retrofit Through Urban Mining	Green Skills	LNEG CECOLAB
LCA Of Prefabricated Envelope Components with Nature-Based Materials for NZEB Retrofitting of a Residential Building	Green Skills	TUC

4. Monitoring and assessment strategies

Monitoring and assessment are essential for ensuring that microcredential-based learning is effective, transparent, and relevant. These processes are particularly important in educational frameworks that address a multidisciplinary audience, including technical professionals, financial/business professionals, students, VET learners, and lifelong learners.

The monitoring and assessment strategy should support the credibility of digital certificates and other forms of digital recognition. In line with the European approach to microcredentials, a microcredential should document learning outcomes acquired after a small volume of learning and should be based on transparent standards and assessment.

4.1. Purpose of monitoring and assessment

The purpose of monitoring is to follow the implementation and quality of the learning process. It helps educators and course providers understand how learners interact with the course, whether the workload is appropriate, whether the digital tools are accessible, and whether any part needs improvement.

The purpose of assessment is to verify whether learners have achieved the expected learning outcomes of each microcredential. Assessment should provide evidence that the learner has acquired the intended knowledge and competences. This is especially important when the completion of a microcredential leads to the issuing of a digital certificate or credential record. Monitoring and assessment should therefore operate together.

The purpose of monitoring and assessment in a microcredential course can be summarised into four main functions (Table 6). Monitoring supports the improvement of the learning experience, while assessment supports the verification and recognition of acquired competences.

Table 6. Four functions of monitoring and assessment

Function	Purpose in the course
Learning support	Help learners check their understanding and progress through the course
Competence verification	Confirm that learning outcomes have been achieved
Quality improvement	Identify weaknesses in content, workload, platform use, assessment
Recognition	Provide reliable evidence for issuing digital certificate or credential record

4.2. Learner assessment strategy

Learner assessment should be directly aligned with the learning outcomes of each microcredential. Since microcredentials are based on clearly defined learning outcomes, the assessment method should verify whether learners can demonstrate the expected competences.

The assessment should not be limited to passive course completion. A learner should receive a badge or certificate only after demonstrating that the intended learning outcomes have been achieved. This principle is important for ensuring the credibility of the microcredentials. Assessment methods should be selected according to the type of competence being assessed. For online and MOOC-based learning, the methods listed in Table 7 can be particularly suitable.

Table 7. Assessment methods in MOOC-based learning

Assessment method	Possible use in the course
Reinforcement questions	Support self-assessment during the course
Multiple-choice quizzes	Check understanding of key concepts and definitions
Final test	Verify achievement of the main learning outcomes at the end of the microcredential
Case-study task	Assess the ability to apply concepts to building renovation scenarios
Calculation exercise	Assess technical or financial analysis skills
Short assignment	Assess interpretation, communication, decision-making skills
Digital tool exercise	Assess the ability to use software, calculation sheets, data-based tools
Reflection test	Encourage learners to connect various perspectives (e.g. technical, financial, sustainability)

The choice of assessment should reflect the objective of the microcredential. For example, a microcredential on energy auditing of buildings may include questions on audit procedures and a practical task requiring learners to identify energy-saving options. A microcredential on green infrastructure finance may include a case-based exercise comparing financing mechanisms. A microcredential on probabilistic evaluation may include exercises on uncertainty, risk analysis, and financial performance indicators. Assessment should follow the principles in Table 8.

Table 8. Principles of course assessment

Principle	Application in the course
Alignment	Each assessment should correspond to one or more learning outcomes
Transparency	Learners should know the assessment criteria before starting the course
Practical relevance	Assessment should reflect realistic professional situations
Flexibility	Assessment should be suitable for online and self-paced learning
Reliability	Assessment should provide consistent evidence of learner achievement
Feedback	Learners should receive information on their performance where possible

4.3. Course monitoring strategy

Course monitoring should be carried out before, during, and after the delivery of each microcredential. Before course launch, educators should check that all learning materials are complete, accessible, and correctly uploaded to the platform. This includes video lectures, subtitles, reading materials, exercises, case studies, quizzes, final tests, and digital resources. The structure of the course should also be reviewed to ensure that the sequence of sections, subsections, and units is logical and manageable for learners.

During course delivery, educators and platform administrators should monitor learner engagement and progression. This may include video views, quiz attempts, completion of units, learner questions, downloads of materials, and technical issues. Special attention should be paid to drop-off points, where learners stop progressing. These points may indicate problems with workload, clarity, difficulty, platform usability, or learner support.

After course completion, monitoring should focus on completion rates, assessment results, learner satisfaction, certificate issuing, and stakeholder feedback. This information should be used to revise the course structure, improve teaching materials, and refine assessment methods. A monitoring framework is presented in Table 9.

Table 9. Monitoring framework for a MOOC-based course

Principle	Application in the course
Access	Number of registered learners, number of active learners
Engagement	Video views, reading downloads, quiz attempts, platform activity
Progression	Completed units, completed sections, drop-off points
Completion	Number and percentage of learners completing the microcredential
Achievement	Assessment results, pass rates, Open Badges issued
Satisfaction	Learner feedback, perceived usefulness, platform usability
Accessibility	Use of subtitles, clarity of materials, reported accessibility issues
Relevance	Stakeholder feedback, employer feedback, Knowledge Centre comments

4.4. Feedback collection and quality assurance

Feedback collection is a key part of monitoring and assessment. It helps ensure that microcredentials remain useful for learners and stakeholders. In SHERLOCK, feedback should be collected from learners, educators, project partners, and stakeholders involved in the Knowledge Centres.

Learner feedback should focus on the learning experience. It should collect information on the clarity of the course structure, quality of video lectures, usefulness of reading materials, relevance of case studies, difficulty of reinforcement questions, workload, platform usability, and overall satisfaction. Educator feedback should focus on the coherence of the learning outcomes, suitability of teaching materials, effectiveness of assessment methods, and challenges encountered during course.

Stakeholder feedback should focus on labour-market relevance. HEI, VET providers, companies, financial institutions, public authorities, professional associations, and Knowledge Centre members should be asked whether the microcredentials respond to real skills needs and whether the learning outcomes are understandable and useful for professional practice.

Feedback can be collected through:

- online questionnaires after each microcredential;
- short surveys after specific course sections;
- interviews with educators and trainers;
- focus groups with learners or stakeholders;
- stakeholder meetings;
- review workshops after piloting;
- analysis of platform data and assessment results.

Quality assurance should be embedded throughout the full life cycle of each microcredential, beginning during the design phase and continuing through development, delivery, assessment, certification, and revision. It should be implemented as a continuous improvement cycle consisting of five phases, as shown in Fig. 6.

Figure 6 – Continuous improvement cycle

4.5. Recommendations for monitoring and assessment

Based on the SHERLOCK approach and the practical examples discussed in Section 5.2, the following recommendations on monitoring and assessment are proposed for educators and training providers:

- (i) **Align assessment with learning outcomes.** Each assessment activity should correspond to one or more learning outcomes.
- (ii) **Use both formative and summative assessment.** Reinforcement questions, short quizzes, exercises support learning during the course. Final tests, assignments should verify achievement at the end.
- (iii) **Practical application, not only theory.** Where possible, assessment should require learners to apply knowledge to realistic situations.
- (iv) **Make badge issuing conditional on assessment.** Open Badges should be issued only when the learner has completed the required activities and demonstrated achievement.
- (v) **Monitor learner engagement continuously.** Educators should use platform data to monitor participation, progression, completion, quiz performance, and drop-off points.
- (vi) **Collect feedback from multiple groups.** Learners, educators, HEI, VET providers, companies, financial institutions, public authorities, professional organisations, etc.

- (vii) **Use monitoring results for improvement.** Monitoring should lead to concrete improvements in videos, readings, case studies, exercises, assessment tasks, workload, accessibility, and platform structure.
- (viii) **Keep microcredentials relevant over time.** Professions can evolve quickly, therefore, microcredentials should be reviewed regularly.
- (ix) **Ensure transparency.** Learners should know the workload, assessment criteria, completion requirements, badge conditions, and expected learning outcomes before starting the course.
- (x) **Maintain consistency across all microcredentials.** The structure, assessment approach, workload, badge metadata, and quality review process should be consistent across the micromaster pathway.

5. Recommendations for microcredential-based teaching and training

5.1. Purpose of integrating innovative teaching tools

The purpose of integrating innovative teaching tools is to make microcredential-based learning structured and effective. Each tool contributes to a specific part of the learning process: videos and readings introduce the content, questions and exercises reinforce understanding, case studies and digital tools support application, and assessments and certificates document the competences achieved.

The teaching tools should be combined into a coherent learning experience. A typical learning scenario may begin with short video lectures introducing the main concepts, followed by reading materials that provide additional background and examples. Reinforcement questions can then be used to support self-assessment and help learners identify whether they have understood the core content. Once the basic knowledge has been acquired, case studies, exercises, calculation sheets, digital tools or simulations can be used to support practical application. The learning sequence concludes with a final assessment. Digital certificates or credential records then provide evidence of the competences acquired by the learner.

In SHERLOCK, the learning pathway is structured around microcredentials delivered through an online learning platform. Each microcredential is organised into sections, subsections and learning units. This structure allows learners to progress gradually from concepts to more advanced and applied content. Table 10 summarises the teaching tools and their role in the SHERLOCK learning process.

Table 10. Main teaching tools and their role in SHERLOCK

Teaching tool	Main function in the course
MOOC platform	Provides flexible and scalable access to learning content
Microcredentials	Organise learning into short, focused and assessable units
Video lectures	Introduce key concepts in a concise and accessible format
Reading materials	Provide additional explanations, examples and technical background
Reinforcement questions	Support self-assessment and consolidation of knowledge
Case studies	Connect theory with real-life multidisciplinary problems
Digital exercises and tools	Support practical application and data-based learning
Final assessments	Verify achievement of learning outcomes
Open Badges	Recognise and communicate acquired competences

The approach allows educators to combine different tools according to the objective of each microcredential. For example, a technically oriented microcredential may place stronger emphasis on simulations, calculations and data analysis, while a financially oriented microcredential may rely more on case studies, decision-making exercises and investment evaluation tasks. A possible structure for integrating teaching tools in a microcredential is shown in Table 11.

Table 11. Example of integrating teaching tools in one microcredential

Learning phase	Teaching tools	Purpose
Introduction	Short videos, course overview	Present the topic, objectives and relevance
Knowledge development	Video lectures, readings, examples	Explain concepts and provide theoretical background
Self-assessment	Reinforcement questions, short quizzes	Help learners check understanding
Practical application	Case studies, exercises, digital tools, calculation sheets	Apply knowledge to realistic problems
Reflection and consolidation	Discussion prompts, summary materials	Connect technical, financial and sustainability aspects
Final assessment	Final test, assignment or task	Verify achievement of learning outcomes
Recognition	Digital certificate or credential record	Certify and communicate acquired competences

5.2. Successful practical examples of microcredential use

Practical applications of microcredentials show that they can support different educational and labour-market objectives. The following examples illustrate how microcredentials and digital credentials are used in professional upskilling, employability, credit recognition and lifelong learning (Table 12).

Table 12. Summary of practical examples of microcredential use

Example	Main role	Why it is relevant
RES4CITY microcredential framework	Methodological framework for creating a microcredential basket	Shows how stakeholder co-design, labour-market analysis, learning outcomes, and stackability can be used to design microcredentials for green-transition skills
Coursera	Online learning platform for professional certificates and credit recognition	Shows how platforms can deliver microcredentials at scale and connect some professional certificates with academic recognition
Google Career Certificates	Industry-designed career credentials	Shows how microcredentials can be structured around job-ready skills, occupational profiles, and practical career development
IBM SkillsBuild	Skills-learning and digital credentialing ecosystem	Shows how digital credentials can make skills visible, portable, verifiable, and understandable to employers

5.2.1. RES4CITY microcredential framework

The RES4CITY microcredential framework provides a particularly relevant case study for multidisciplinary teaching methods based on microcredentials. Its main strength is that microcredentials were not designed only from an academic perspective, but through a process combining stakeholder consultation, focus groups, surveys, and AI-supported analysis of job descriptions. This made it possible to identify skills required by the labour market and translate them into a basket of 74 multidisciplinary microcredentials for learners with both technical and non-technical backgrounds.

Another important element of the RES4CITY framework is the use of a student-centred and lifelong-learning approach. Microcredentials are especially suitable for professionals because they are short, focused, flexible and designed to address specific skills needed in the job market. This makes them useful for upskilling and reskilling, particularly in sectors affected by rapid technological, environmental and policy change.

The RES4CITY methodology also provides a useful model for learning objective definition. After identifying educational needs, the project translated them into learning objectives and microcredential topics. The framework used structured classification elements, including EQF levels, ECTS workload and discipline classification, to organise the microcredential basket.

A particularly useful lesson from RES4CITY is the importance of combining stakeholder engagement with data-driven evidence. Stakeholder consultation helped identify perceived needs and practical expectations, while job-market analysis provided additional evidence on the skills currently requested by employers. In RES4CITY, AI and natural language processing were used to

analyse job advertisements and classify skills into categories such as soft skills, knowledge-based skills and technical skills.

Compared with SHERLOCK, RES4CITY is the most directly comparable example because it also focuses on green-transition skills and uses a structured methodology for developing a microcredential basket. Both approaches rely on stakeholder input, learning-outcome definition, multidisciplinary content, and the idea of stackable microcredentials. Both projects confirm the importance of designing microcredentials through a structured process.

5.2.2. Coursera professional certificates and credit recognition

Coursera is primarily an online learning platform rather than a single certification scheme. It hosts courses, professional certificates, guided projects, and degree programmes developed by universities, companies, and other organisations. Coursera functions mainly as a platform and ecosystem for online credentials, although it also offers structured learning formats under the Coursera brand.

Coursera Professional Certificates provide job-oriented online learning pathways developed with companies and institutions. These programmes are designed to help learners gain job-relevant skills and apply their knowledge through practical activities. Coursera also reports that several Google and IBM Professional Certificates received ECTS credit recommendations, supporting the possibility of recognising job-relevant online credentials in academia.

The case is relevant because Coursera Professional Certificates are usually developed in cooperation with major companies and institutions, including Google, IBM, Meta, Microsoft, Salesforce and others. This gives the credentials a strong labour-market orientation. The certificates are not structured only around academic topics, but around practical skills needed for specific occupational areas such as data analytics, cybersecurity, project management, UX design, digital marketing, software development and IT support.

A key strength of the Coursera model is the use of applied learning. Many Professional Certificates include hands-on projects, labs, portfolio activities or practical assignments that allow learners to demonstrate what they can do. Coursera states that its Professional Certificates help learners apply knowledge to hands-on projects that showcase skills to employers.

Another important aspect of Coursera Professional Certificates is their connection with credit recognition. In 2024, Coursera announced that the Foundation for International Business Administration Accreditation (FIBAA) had certified 12 Google and IBM Professional Certificates, with European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System (ECTS) credit recommendations available. The list includes certificates such as Google Data Analytics, Google Project

Management, Google IT Support, IBM Data Science, IBM Cybersecurity Analyst, IBM Data Analyst, with recommended ECTS credits varying by certificate. This shows how online professional credentials can move beyond informal recognition and become connected to formal education systems.

Coursera also provides examples of Professional Certificates linked to both academic and industry recognition. For instance, the IBM Data Science Professional Certificate is described as ACE [10] and FIBAA recommended, with learners able to earn up to 12 college credits and 6 ECTS credits after completion. It also includes hands-on labs in IBM Cloud to build practical skills applicable to real jobs.

Coursera is different from SHERLOCK because it mainly represents a digital platform for delivering online courses and professional certificates, while SHERLOCK represents a project-based example of designing a microcredential framework for building renovation. Coursera illustrates how platform-based learning can operate at a broader international scale and how some professional certificates can be connected to academic credit recognition.

5.2.3. Google career certificates

Google Career Certificates [11] are an example of industry-led microcredentials designed to provide job-ready skills in high-demand fields. They cover areas such as IT Support, Project Management, Data Analytics, UX Design, Digital Marketing and E-Commerce, and Cybersecurity. The certificates are delivered through flexible online training and are designed to help learners acquire practical skills that can be applied in their professions.

The certificates are structured for learners who may not have previous experience in the field. They combine self-paced online learning with hands-on practice and assessments. On Coursera, for example, the Google Project Management Professional Certificate is presented as beginner-level, requiring no degree or prior experience, and is organised as a multi-course learning pathway with flexible scheduling.

A key strength of the Google model is that each certificate is linked to a clearly defined occupational profile. Instead of offering general digital education, each pathway is designed around a target role or professional field. This makes the learning outcomes easier to understand. The practical orientation is also reinforced through applied activities, assessments and job-search support, including guidance related to CVs and job applications.

For educators, the Google Career Certificates case shows the importance of designing microcredentials around concrete competences rather than broad topics. Each certificate answers three practical questions: who the learner is,

which role or professional need the credential supports, and which skills the learner should be able to demonstrate after completion. The Google example is also useful because it shows how online learning can be organised as a coherent pathway. Learners progress through a sequence of courses or units, complete exercises and assessments, and receive a credential.

Another relevant aspect is employer visibility. Google Career Certificates are designed to support access to employment and career development, and some versions of the programme include opportunities to connect with employers after completion. This is important because the value of microcredentials increases when employers, professional organisations, VET providers and financial institutions understand what the credential represents.

Compared with SHERLOCK, Google Career Certificates are more directly oriented towards job-ready skills for specific occupational profiles, such as IT support, data analytics, project management, cybersecurity. The Google example shows the importance of designing credentials around clearly defined professional needs, whereas SHERLOCK mainly addresses the skills mismatch between technical and financial actors in building renovation.

5.2.4. IBM SkillsBuild digital credentials

[12] SkillsBuild provides online learning and digital credentials that allow learners to showcase skills and achievements to employers. The platform highlights portability and matching between candidates and jobs as important benefits of digital credentials.

The case is relevant because IBM SkillsBuild connects three elements that are also important for SHERLOCK: online learning, competence-based recognition, and labour-market communication. IBM explains that the received credentials are industry-recognised and represent skills, knowledge, and competence achievements that are meaningful for learners and useful for employers.

A key strength of the IBM model is the explicit focus on skills validation. IBM also highlights portability, security, increased visibility, and better matching between candidates and jobs as key benefits of digital credentials. Credentials are stored online, can be accessed from anywhere, and can be shared with employers, educational institutions, or other organisations.

IBM SkillsBuild also illustrates how digital credentials can support different stages of learning. The platform includes credentials for foundational knowledge, practical skills, professional skills, and career-oriented pathways. For example, the “AI Fundamentals” credential demonstrates foundational knowledge of artificial intelligence concepts, machine learning, neural networks, AI ethics, and responsible use of AI tools. The “Agile Explorer” badge

demonstrates understanding of agile values, principles, and practices that can be applied in academic or workplace environments.

The IBM example also highlights the importance of making credentials understandable to employers. A badge should be easy to interpret by a company, financial institution, public authority, VET provider, or professional association. For example, a SHERLOCK badge for “Communication strategies with financial institutions” should indicate that the learner can understand financing criteria, prepare documentation, and support negotiation processes.

5.3. Practical recommendations for educators

The practical examples presented in Section 5.2 show that successful microcredentials are not simply short online courses. They are structured learning experiences with clear professional relevance, measurable learning outcomes, appropriate assessment, digital recognition, and links to labour-market needs. Based on these examples, the SHERLOCK experience, and the methodology described in the previous chapters, the following recommendations are provided. They are organised according to the main phases of designing and implementing microcredential-based learning.

5.3.1 Educational needs identification and assessment

The development of microcredentials should start with the identification of educational needs. Educators first define who the learners are, what their professional or educational background is, and which competences they need to acquire or improve. This step is essential because microcredentials should respond to clearly identified skills gaps.

Educational needs assessment should combine different sources of information. These may include stakeholder consultation, labour-market analysis, policy priorities, learner feedback, and previous project experience. In multidisciplinary fields, the analysis should consider both sector-specific and transversal skills. For example, in the SHERLOCK context, educational needs are linked to the skills mismatch between technical and financial actors involved in building energy renovation.

Educators are therefore recommended to:

- define the target learner groups and their prior knowledge;
- identify the professional problem that the microcredential should address;
- identify the different types of skills and competences required, including technical, digital, transversal, and professional skills;

- use stakeholder and labour-market evidence to validate the identified gaps;
- translate the identified needs into priority areas.

Each microcredential should also include a short statement explaining its professional relevance. This statement should clarify who the microcredential is for, what practical problem it addresses, and how the acquired competences can be used in professional practice.

5.3.2 Stakeholder co-design framework

Microcredentials should not be developed only by individual teachers or academic institutions. A stakeholder co-design framework should be established to ensure that the learning offer reflects real professional and labour-market needs. Stakeholder co-design means involving relevant actors including higher education institutions, VET providers, companies, employers, financial institutions, public authorities, professional associations, learners, platform providers and sector experts.

Educators are recommended to:

- identify relevant stakeholders before finalising the microcredential topics;
- involve stakeholders in skills-gap identification and validation;
- use surveys, interviews, workshops or focus groups to collect input;
- ask stakeholders to review the learning outcomes and validate professional relevance;
- document stakeholder input as part of the quality assurance process.

Stakeholder involvement should not be treated as a one-time consultation. It should continue during development, piloting, feedback collection and revision of the microcredentials.

5.3.3 Learning objectives and microcredential definition

Learning objectives should be defined after the target learners and educational needs are clear. They should describe what learners will know or be able to do after completing the microcredential. Learning objectives should be specific, measurable, and suitable for assessment. Vague formulations such as “understand the topic” should be avoided. Instead, learning outcomes should use action-oriented wording, such as “identify energy-saving measures”, “evaluate financing options” or “compare renovation scenarios”.

After learning outcomes are defined, related outcomes should be grouped into microcredential topics. Each microcredential should focus on a clearly defined

competence area and should have standalone value. At the same time, individual microcredentials should complement each other and contribute to a broader learning pathway, such as a micromaster or training programme.

Educators are recommended to:

- define learning outcomes using clear action verbs;
- ensure that each learning outcome can be assessed;
- avoid overly broad or vague learning objectives;
- group related learning outcomes into focused microcredential topics;
- ensure that each microcredential has standalone value;
- ensure that microcredentials are stackable within a wider pathway;
- include learning outcomes in the certificate or badge.

Table 13 presents the minimum information that should be available for each microcredential. The same information may also be included in the corresponding digital certificate or credential record to make the achievement informative and easy to verify.

Table 13. Minimum information to include in a microcredential

Element	Information
Target group	Technical professionals, financial/business professionals, VET learners, HEI students, or mixed audience
Professional relevance	What practical sector needs the microcredential addresses
Learning outcomes	4–6 measurable outcomes using action verbs
Workload	ECTS value, estimated hours, weekly effort
Level	EQF level and prerequisites, where relevant
Learning materials	Videos, readings, slides, exercises, case studies, tools
Assessment	Quiz, final test, assignment, case-study task, or practical exercise
Badge information	Issuer, title, learning outcomes, assessment criteria, workload, date, skills tags
Stakeholder input	Evidence that content was validated by educators, industry, VET providers, or Knowledge Centre members
Quality review	Learner feedback, completion data, assessment results, and revision plan

5.3.4 Micromaster structure

A micromaster should be designed as a coherent learning pathway composed of several microcredentials. The structure should show how individual microcredentials contribute to the competence profile. It should clarify which microcredentials are common for all learners and which are specific to particular target groups.

In multidisciplinary education, this structure is especially useful when different learner groups need complementary competences. For example, one pathway may provide technical learners with financial and business competences, while another pathway may provide financial or business learners with technical and environmental knowledge, like in SHERLOCK.

Educators are recommended to:

- define the overall competence profile of the micromaster;
- decide which microcredentials are common and which are group specific;
- ensure consistency in workload, level, structure and assessment across all microcredentials;
- prepare teaching materials that directly support the learning outcomes;
- ensure each material has a clear function in helping learners achieve the competence;
- use short and focused videos;
- provide downloadable readings, slides, examples, exercises, tools;
- include case studies and applied tasks where practical competences are expected;
- ensure accessibility through subtitles, clear instructions and realistic workload.

5.3.5 Monitoring and assessment strategies

Monitoring and assessment should be planned from the beginning of the microcredential design process. Digital certificates or credential records should be issued only when learners have completed the required activities and demonstrated achievement of the expected competences. This strengthens the credibility of the credential and makes it meaningful for learners and employers.

Educators are recommended to:

- align every assessment activity with one or more learning outcomes;
- use reinforcement questions for self-assessment;
- use final summative tests or assignments to verify achievement;
- include applied tasks where learners need to demonstrate practical competences;
- make badge issuing conditional on assessment;
- monitor learner engagement, progress and completion;
- identify drop-off points and sections where learners struggle;
- collect feedback from learners, educators and stakeholders;
- revise materials regularly based on evidence.

Useful monitoring indicators include enrolment, active learners, completion rates, quiz performance, final assessment results, drop-off points, badge issuing

and learner feedback. Monitoring should lead to concrete improvements in videos, readings, case studies, exercises, assessment tasks, workload, accessibility and platform structure.

5.3.6 Integration and utilization of innovative teaching tools

Innovative teaching tools should not be treated as separate or disconnected elements. Videos, readings, reinforcement questions, case studies, digital tools, exercises, assessments and certificates should each have a clear role in the learning process. They should be integrated into one coherent learning pathway.

A useful learning sequence may begin with short videos introducing the topic, followed by readings and examples that develop knowledge. Reinforcement questions can then support self-assessment. Case studies, exercises, calculation sheets, simulations or digital tools can support practical application. The sequence should conclude with a final assessment and, where appropriate, digital recognition through a digital certificate or credential record.

Educators are recommended to:

- combine different learning tools instead of relying only on video lectures;
- use case studies as active learning tasks, not only as reading material;
- use digital tools to support practical application;
- connect each teaching tool to a specific learning outcome;
- include reflection activities where learners connect different points of view;
- use digital certificates or credential records to communicate acquired competences;
- make the professional value of each microcredential explicit.

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